

DiSSCo Flanders 2.0: Quantitative and qualitative impact analysis

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1. Introduction

1.1. Overview of DiSSCo and DiSSCo Flanders

Natural science collections are critical for understanding biodiversity, environmental change, and ecosystem functioning. They serve as foundational data sources across a range of scientific fields, including taxonomy, ecology, evolution, palaeontology, and geology. They are also crucial in addressing urgent societal challenges like biodiversity loss, invasive species, climate change, global health, food security, sustainable agriculture, fisheries, and mineral resource depletion. Despite their importance, many collections remain fragmented and inaccessible.

The Distributed System of Scientific Collections (**DiSSCo**) is a European Research Infrastructure (RI) that aims to address this issue by digitally unifying and managing natural science collections across 23 countries. By transforming physical specimens into FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Digital Objects, DiSSCo enhances the accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data, enabling new forms of research and innovation.

Within the European RI, **DiSSCo Flanders** contributes by:

- Unlocking collections in the Flemish institutions, both physically and digitally.
- Ensuring the long-term preservation of the collections.
- Integrating Flemish institutions into the European infrastructure.
- Developing innovative services (see below).
- Promoting public engagement.

1.2. Services and users

DiSSCo Flanders supports a diverse and expanding portfolio of **key services**, which include:

- Physical and digital **access** to collections.
- Integration with the **DiSSCo RI** and international infrastructures (e.g. GBIF, GeoCAsE).
- **Data-linkage services**, supporting fundamental (e.g. taxonomy, ecology), and applied research.
- **Crowdsourcing platform** for collection transcription and enrichment, and engaging citizens in collection management and research.
- **Machine learning** and **biodiversity information tools** to automate collection curation and data enrichment.
- **Best practices** for **collection management** and legal/ethical compliance.

Users primarily include the international research community, but also a wide range of groups that support research, translate collection-based findings into policy, engage, and inform the public, or apply the data in commercial contexts. Key user groups include:

- **Researchers** in both fundamental and applied biological and geological sciences. Fundamental research fields include taxonomy, biogeography, ecology, phylogenetics, evolution, palaeontology, paleoecology, geology, soil sciences, and the history of science. Applied research areas address urgent societal challenges such as biodiversity loss, invasive species, climate change, global health, food security, sustainable agriculture and fisheries, and the depletion of natural resources.
- **Collection managers** and **curators**, who use DiSSCo services and tools to improve collection management, digitisation workflows, and data integration.
- **Policy-makers** and **governmental agencies**, particularly in contexts such as environmental impact assessments, biodiversity monitoring, and conservation planning.
- **Educators** and **students**, who use collections for teaching, learning, and academic research.
- **Citizen scientists** and the **general public**, who engage with the collections through crowdsourcing platforms, exhibitions, and outreach programmes.
- **Exhibition developers** and museum professionals, who use specimens and collection data to create informative and engaging public displays.
- **Private sector stakeholders**, particularly those involved in the natural sciences or working with biological, geological, or other natural resources (e.g., timber identification, pharmaceutical discovery, environmental consulting).

1.3. Tracking usage of DiSSCo Flanders' collections and services

At the start of the DiSSCo Flanders project (2021), an initial set of Key Performance Indicators (**KPIs**) was defined. As the infrastructure is still in construction, these KPIs have been updated and refined for DiSSCo Flanders 2.0 to better align with the optimised metrics required by DiSSCo-EU. The new KPIs also better align with metrics used by GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility) to measure the usage and citing of collection specimens. By using the GBIF hosted portal tool, the DiSSCo Flanders Portal can deliver similar metrics specifically about the Flemish collections.

Initial KPIs DiSSCo Flanders (2021-2024)

1. Number of Collections and items inventoried (yearly basis).
2. Number of Collections and items state assessed (yearly basis).
3. Number of Collections and items published in the GRSciColl registry (yearly basis)
4. Number of Collections opened to transnational access (years 2 and 4).
5. Number of Collections part of Virtual access (years 2 and 4).

Revised KPIs DiSSCo Flanders 2.0 (2025-2028)

Collections-related KPIs

1. Number of digitised specimens available within the institutional collection management systems (CMS) (yearly basis).
2. Number of online published collections and specimens: (a) in the GRSciColl registry and (b) in institutional portals (e.g. botanicalcollections.be, www.blendeff.be) and data aggregators (e.g. GBIF, GeoCase, and eventually the future DiSSCo portal) (yearly basis).
3. Use of collections for research and the general public, measured as number of loan requests and number of scientific visitor days to the collections (research), and number of public visitors to the collections, including museums, botanical gardens, and zoos (general public) (years 2 and 4).

Scientific impact KPI

4. Number of scientific publications using collections or collection-based data (based on GBIF metrics) (year 2 and 4).

Citizen engagement KPI

5. Number of collection items transcribed via the [DoeDat](#) crowdsourcing platform (yearly basis).

ESFRI-wide KPIs

In collaboration with the other research infrastructures (RIs) in Flanders, DiSSCo Flanders will lead an exercise of defining specific KPIs on research infrastructures that aim to obtain an objective measurement of impact. This should go beyond the classical parameters used for science, but take into account the indirect impact of the infrastructures on policy, but also on engagement and outreach towards the general public. This will create a more complete picture of the total benefits of the research infrastructures and monitor the impacts of the RIs over time.

2. Impact

2.1 Realised Impact (2020–2024)

Efforts within the first DiSSCo Flanders project have significantly enhanced the visibility of collections, both in physical and digital formats. Inventory information can now be easily accessed through the DiSSCo Flanders [Collections Digitization Dashboard](#). Some collections have been fully digitised and are accessible through institutional portals, the DiSSCo Flanders portal, and GBIF. Moreover, the groundwork has been established for additional collections to become accessible, aided by the implementation of tools such as

adherence to data standards and the establishment of necessary infrastructure such as collection management systems. Additionally, a citizen crowdsourcing platform for enriching specimen data is already operational and will be further developed in the DiSSCo Flanders 2.0 project.

2.2.1. Quantitative impact (KPIs)

A comprehensive overview of the KPIs from the first DiSSCo Flanders project (2021–2024) is provided in the [final project report](#). For full details, we refer to that report rather than repeating the information here.

2.2.2. Qualitative impact

- **Infrastructure development:** Implementation of collection management systems (CMS) across partner institutions, including Meise Botanic Garden, KU Leuven, ILVO, and INBO, significantly improved digital management of collections.
- **Collection inventory:** Systematic inventory of the different collections and publication on the [Collection Dashboard](#) increased the visibility of the Flemish collections.
- **Collection management:** Development and adoption of best practices and workflows for managing different collection types (including molecular collections), and investment to enhance collection organisation and accessibility increased the accessibility and usability of collections.
- **Training:** Staff training initiatives strengthened institutional expertise in digitisation, data handling, and collection curation.
- **Citizen engagement:** Engagement of citizen scientists through the DoeDat crowdsourcing platform.
- **Improved collaboration:** Collaboration between Flemish, federal and European institutions resulted in a more integrated research infrastructure ecosystem.
- **Technical leadership:** DiSSCo Flanders played a leading role in advancing the technical foundations for the DiSSCo RI, contributing innovative solutions and tools.

2.2 Expected Impact (2025–2028)

Collection data mobilised by DiSSCo Flanders will significantly advance fundamental and applied research, spanning fields from biodiversity and genomics to climate change, invasive species, and ecosystem health. These data will also support innovation in environmental monitoring, food security, health, and the bioeconomy.

As part of the European Open Science movement, DiSSCo actively promotes FAIR principles, ensuring biodiversity data are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. This stimulates transparent, collaborative research and supports compliance with legal frameworks such as the Nagoya Protocol, advocating ethical and equitable research practices.

Beyond scientific research, DiSSCo Flanders will reach the wider public through education and citizen science initiatives. Collections featured in museums, botanic gardens, and zoos enhance public understanding of biodiversity and inspire engagement in conservation and scientific research.

DiSSCo Flanders 2.0 will serve as a catalyst for attracting new research projects and funding. Participation in the DiSSCo RI promotes international collaboration with experts in natural science collections, biodiversity informatics, and geo- and biodiversity research. The growing visibility of Flemish collections and institutional expertise increases opportunities for external funding and new partnerships. Recent examples include several European, and nationally or FWO-funded projects. Over the next four years, additional funding is expected through EU programmes linked to EOSC and related initiatives.

2.2.1. Expected quantitative impact (KPIs)

Over the next four years, DiSSCo Flanders expects a steady increase in digitised specimens within institutional collection management systems (KPI 1), and published collections and specimens in the the Global Registry of Scientific Collections (GRSciColl), institutional portals, and international aggregators such as GBIF (KPI 2).

This growing digital presence is anticipated to enhance collection usage across research domains (KPI 3), leading to a measurable rise in scientific impact, reflected by an increase of publications using collection-based data (KPI 4).

In parallel, the redevelopment and European deployment of a crowdsourcing platform will significantly increase citizen science engagement, increasing the number of transcribed collection items (KPI 5).

2.2.2. Expected qualitative impact

DiSSCo Flanders 2.0 is expected to bring important improvements to the European RI through new technologies, better infrastructure, and stronger research and public engagement. Key areas of impact include:

- **Digital innovation and tool development.** The project will deliver advanced tools such as AI-powered image segmentation, IIIF-compliant digital access frameworks, and enhanced taxonomic services. These outputs will enhance specimen digitisation and data linking.
- **Novel research enabled by linked open data.** Enriched and linked data will support new research across a wide range of disciplines. Flemish digital specimens are already informing studies in: taxonomy, evolution, biogeography, ecology, biodiversity conservation, species tracing, environmental and climate change research, and citizen science. We expect that research fields that make use of collections will expand in the coming years.

- **Scientific output and collaboration.** The digitisation of collections is expected to further stimulate research and collaborative projects and increase scientific publications across the consortium partners, as well as at European and international level.
- A performant **crowdsourcing platform** will increase citizen science participation at a European scale.
- **Improved collection management.** Specific working groups will improve institutional collection management practices, with specific improvements in DNA and molecular collections, as well as Earth Sciences collections. Best practices will be developed and shared across institutions.
- **Collection preservation.** Enhanced physical curation will ensure long-term preservation of collections through the adoption of international standards and best practices.
- **Coordination at national level.** DiSSCo Flanders will reinforce national coordination within Belgium and continue to contribute actively to the development of the DiSSCo ERIC, ensuring alignment with European strategies and priorities.

2.3. Valorisation potential

DiSSCo Flanders is primarily a research infrastructure that supports both fundamental and applied science. Beyond its scientific role, it also offers significant potential for societal, educational, and economic valorisation. Societal and educational impact includes increased public engagement through citizen science, as well as enhanced biodiversity awareness through education at universities. Additionally, natural science collections provide valuable reference materials for private sector applications, and DiSSCo Flanders is committed to further expanding this impact.

A selection of societal, educational, and economic valorisation examples within the DiSSCo Flanders consortium includes, though is not limited to:

- **Wood collection for timber traceability.** The wood collection at Meise Botanic Garden serves as an important reference for timber identification and research. Using georeferenced specimens and spatial models, it enables analyses to trace timber origins, helping combat illegal logging and promote sustainable forest management. As a partner in World Forest ID, Meise Botanic Garden contributes to global wood traceability efforts.
- **Fish tissue collection aids reconstructing the evolution in forever chemical pollution.** Samples from the INBO fish tissue collection were analysed on 42 PFAS components to understand the magnitude and spread of these pollutants. An analysis of samples collected between 2000 and 2008 on 28 locations in Flanders clearly demonstrated that PFAS was already widespread in Flemish waterways, with several locations exceeding safe concentrations for aquatic ecosystems and human health. In comparison to recent studies, concentrations dropped considerably over a period of 20 years for most locations. Despite this generally positive evolution, there is still a long way to go for reaching current safety norms. This collection proved invaluable in tracking the evolution of persistent chemicals and the impact of policy

measures, and will continue to do so in the future.

- **Sustainable fisheries through otoliths.** The use of ILVO's fish otoliths for age determination provides critical data on fish population structure, growth rates, and recruitment patterns, which are essential for sustainable fisheries management. By enabling accurate stock assessments, otolith analysis supports the development of science-based catch limits and conservation strategies, thereby helping to maintain fishery productivity, protect marine biodiversity, and secure the long-term livelihoods of communities.
- **Resilient farming with the help of soil and seed collections.** Climate change, biodiversity loss, and increasing international trade are intensifying the threat of crop diseases and pests, with direct consequences for food security and agricultural economies. At ILVO, we develop integrated, science-based solutions that protect crops, by preventing disease outbreaks. This is done through researching sustainable soil management and soil health, and through the selection of disease-resistant crop varieties. This approach contributes to more resilient farming systems and supports sustainable food production.
- **Living collections as harvesting locations for forest plantation production.** The living collections of trees and shrubs included within DiSSCo, contain registered 'parent trees' (Forest Reproductive Material (FRM)) from which seeds can be harvested by recognised tree-nurserymen. The production and sale of forest trees is regulated by a European directive, translated into Flemish legislation. The collections serve as Forest Reproductive Material for the certification of forest trees with the aim of guaranteeing high quality nursery material. These trees are checked for characteristics that contribute to more resilient forests, e.g. tolerance to diseases and better adaptation to local climatic and ecological conditions. By establishing collections of living trees as seed sources (Forest Reproductive Material), more harvesting opportunities are realised for the Flemish tree nursery sector.
- **Diatom collection: supporting water quality monitoring and biodiversity research.** The diatom collection at Meise Botanic Garden, one of the largest in the world, plays a key role in water quality monitoring and environmental assessment in Flanders. Historic and recent specimens support diatom identification critical for ecological monitoring. In collaboration with Flemish agencies such as the Flanders Environment Agency (VMM), the collection forms a vital resource for long-term water quality assessments and biodiversity studies.

3. Lessons learned (2020–2024)

- Coordination, collaboration, and training across partner institutions proved critical for the successful digital mobilisation of collection data.
- Challenges in implementing and standardising collection management systems (CMS) across diverse institutions highlighted the need for adaptable technical solutions and shared best practices.
- Investments in staff training and knowledge-sharing were vital for improving digitisation workflows and enhancing institutional capabilities.
- The success of the DNA collection working group showed the value of focused,

thematic collaborations. This model should be expanded to other collection types (e.g., Earth Sciences, palaeontology).

- Community-driven digitisation efforts (e.g. using volunteers) and the integration of citizen science (e.g., via the DoeDat platform) significantly enhanced data enrichment and public engagement.
- Strong links with federal and European partners enabled alignment with broader RI strategies and increased the visibility and influence of DiSSCo Flanders.
- There is a continued need to refine and expand impact indicators, particularly in collaboration with other ESFRI's, to better capture scientific, societal, and policy-related impact.

4. Position in the Flemish, Belgian and European research infrastructure landscape

4.1 Institutional integration

- DiSSCo Flanders brings together all major collection-holding institutions in Flanders, including universities and research institutes, creating a unified network for biodiversity and geodiversity collections.
- The DiSSCo Flanders consortium collaborates closely with federal institutions and French-speaking universities, strengthening ties across Belgium's administrative boundaries, which is important for the functioning of the Belgian national node of DiSSCo.
- DiSSCo Flanders maintains strong links with other research infrastructures, such as ELIXIR, EMBRC, LifeWatch ERIC and CLARIAH-VL. This enables coordinated data sharing and technology development.

4.2 Strategic added value

- DiSSCo holds a unique position in the European research infrastructure landscape, focussing on the digital unification of natural science collections.
- DiSSCo Flanders plays a key role for Flanders' contribution to the European DiSSCo ERIC, both in technical development and policy representation.
- Beyond infrastructure, DiSSCo Flanders delivers services such as training, public engagement, and legal/ethical guidance for physical and digital collection management.
- The diverse institutional network and collaborative model of DiSSCo Flanders offer strong potential for expanding best-practices across the European RI landscape.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

CLARIAH-VL: Open Humanities Service Infrastructure. The Flemish contribution to the European DARIAH and CLARIN infrastructures.

CMS: Collection Management System. Software systems used to manage and curate natural science collections.

DiSSCo: Distributed System of Scientific Collections (www.dissco.eu).

DoeDat: A crowdsourcing platform managed by Meise Botanic Garden for transcribing and enriching natural science collection data.

ELIXIR: European life sciences infrastructure (elixir-europe.org).

EMBRIC: European Marine Biological Resource Centre (www.embric.eu).

EOSC: European Open Science Cloud. A European initiative to provide a virtual environment for open science (eosc.eu).

ESFRI: European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures.

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable. Principles for managing scientific data to enhance its usability.

GBIF: Global Biodiversity Information Facility. An international network and data infrastructure for biodiversity data (www.gbif.org).

GeoCAsE: Geosciences Collection Access Service. A data portal for geoscientific and fossil collections (geocase.eu).

GRSciColl: Global Registry of Scientific Collections. A registry hosted by GBIF to track institutional and collection data (scientific-collections.gbif.org).

IIF: International Image Interoperability Framework. A standard for presenting digital images online.

LifeWatch: European Research Infrastructure Consortium for biodiversity and ecosystem research (www.lifewatch.eu).

VMM: Flanders Environment Agency (vmm.be)